

EXPLORING THE MEDIATING ROLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT IN THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT AND JOB SATISFACTION TO ENHANCE EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

MUHLIS KHARUNO HALID ¹, ABDUL HADI SIRAT ² and RUSMAN SOLEMAN ³

^{1,2,3} Universitas Khairun, Ternate, Indonesia.

¹Email: muhlishalid21@gmail.com

Abstract

This research aims to obtain empirical evidence regarding the influence of employee engagement and job satisfaction on employee performance through organizational commitment as a mediating variable for employees at the Office of Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia. This research is quantitative. The data was collected through the survey method utilizing interviews and Likert scale questionnaires. The analysis employed Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) facilitated by the SmartPLS 3.29 application. The sample for this research was 79 respondents who worked at the Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia office. The key findings indicate (1) a positive and significant influence of employee engagement on employee performance; (2) a positive and significant impact of job satisfaction on employee performance; (3) a positive and significant influence of organizational commitment on employee performance; (4) a positive and significant influence of employee engagement on organizational commitment; (5) a positive and significant impact of job satisfaction on organizational commitment; (6) an indirect influence of employee engagement on employee performance mediated through organizational commitment; and (7) an indirect influence of job satisfaction on employee performance, mediated through organizational commitment among employees in the Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia office. Practically, this research underscores the importance of strategically focusing on initiatives and programs to enhance employee engagement. By doing so, organizations can elevate job satisfaction levels, fostering stronger employee commitment for sustained organizational growth.

Keywords: Employee Engagement, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

The Strengthening Social Forestry (SSF) Project in Indonesia is a joint grant project between the Global Environment Facility (GEF) distributed through The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (World Bank) and the Government of Indonesia. This project is implemented by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK) c.q. Directorate of Social Forestry Area Preparation (Dit. PKPS), Directorate General of Social Forestry and Environmental Partnership (Ditjen. PSKL). Based on the TF0B2430 Grant Agreement signed on June 17, 2020, by the MoEF and the World Bank, this project will be implemented in 2021 and will last until 2025. SSF Project activity locations in six districts/cities in four provinces, namely (i) Lima Puluh Kota Regency, West Sumatra Province; (ii) South Lampung Regency, Lampung Province; (iii) Bima City, Bima Regency; and (iv) Dompu Regency in West Nusa Tenggara Province; and (v) in West Halmahera Regency, Maluku Province. The SSF Project aims to increase community access rights to forest areas in priority areas for social forestry

development. The project targets 300,000 ha of forest area to be sustainably managed by local communities through social forestry schemes, improving welfare for at least 150,000 people and contributing to the absorption of 9.2 MtCO₂e of Greenhouse Gas (GHG).

Organizations at the Strengthening Social Forestry (SSF) Project in Indonesia need human resources to mobilize other resources. The quality of the human resources themselves greatly influences the success of an organization. These human resources will be of good quality and performance if led and managed appropriately. To manage human resources well, every leader must understand human resource management problems well (Priambodo, 2021). Facing these situations and conditions, an organization must carry out management strategies and policies appropriately, especially in human resources (Hermawan, 2023). Superior resources with high quality are the demands of every organization to achieve the goals set (Alkaresi, 2021). Quality human resources can be seen from the performance of their employees (Hartawan & Sriathi, 2023).

According to Kadri et al. (2023), Employee performance is the actual achievement of the employee compared to the expected achievement of the employee. When companies can give employees what they want, their performance will increase (Rizwandha, 2020). Several factors affect employee performance, including enthusiasm, company-provided facilities, colleagues, and commitment (Alkaresi, 2021). Employee engagement can also affect employee performance and can be seen in completing tasks. Employee engagement shown with enthusiasm at work can also greatly impact employee performance because, with enthusiasm, employees will quickly complete the tasks given by the company (Badrianto & Maryadi, 2023). In a company, employee performance is very important for the sustainability of the company itself. Rizky (2020) defines performance as an employee who shows his behavior with work results when completing his work. Hali (2019) explained that a company's success also cannot be separated from the intervention of an employee, with employee attachment increasing an employee's commitment to his work in the company. Employees who have a high attachment to work result in an employee will not change work to another place because they have a high commitment to their company. The commitment possessed by an employee in the company can also improve one's performance in completing their work (Destika, 2022).

Commitment is one of the important instruments for improving organizational performance (Noercahyo et al., 2021). Through research, Sari (2021) also proves that organizational commitment positively affects employee performance. In addition, Dami et al. (2022) also found a positive influence between organizational commitment and performance. Allen & Meyer (1990) and Priambodo (2021) define organizational commitment as the attitude of employees to be loyal to the company and keep working as well as possible. Commitment is divided into affective commitment, which is the emotional desire of employees to adapt to existing values to remain in the organization. Normative commitment is a sense of moral responsibility to stay in the organization. A high level of employee commitment and performance can be encouraged through employee engagement (Noviardy & Aliya, 2020). This study is distinguished from previous research because it uses job satisfaction as a mediation variable—selection of job satisfaction variables by considering the important role of job

satisfaction in an organization. Job satisfaction is important for employees to remain committed to the company. When an employee is satisfied with his workplace environment, this will impact employee engagement and improve employee performance. Tho'in and Muliasari (2020) added that if employees are not satisfied with their work, they cannot do it according to their norms and expectations.

Based on employee performance reports at the Office of Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia, it is known that employees cannot complete their tasks properly and on target by predetermined targets, some employees cannot perform their work functions independently without intervention, and some employees still often come not on time to the office. This phenomenon indicates a problem related to employee performance. Son et al. (2020) found that one of the variables that can affect employee performance is job satisfaction. Indications of low employee job satisfaction are known from some employees complaining about the salary system that is still lacking and sometimes not by the work that has been done, lack of promotion opportunities, monotonous work, and the presence of employees who are lazy while working which indicates a decrease in employee job satisfaction. Hartawan Sriathi (2023) stated that increasing job satisfaction will affect employee work performance, positively influencing company goals. According to the results of an interview with the head of Section Region I, Mrs. Lentjie Leleulya, information was obtained that another factor causing the decline in employee performance was low organizational commitment. An indication of low organizational commitment to employees at the Office of Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia, where some employees do not care about the work done, employees who work apply the pattern of coming, completing tasks given by the company and then just going home, so that employees feel less attached to the company. In addition, the lack of a sense of kinship in the company causes some employees to feel less comfortable staying in this company.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Performance

Performance is an important thing that the company must manage to achieve a goal. One factor that ensures a company's success is how human resources can contribute maximally to achieving the targets and goals set (Mahmudi, 2009). According to Mathis Jackson (2016), performance is what employees do or do not do. According to Dessler (2016), Employee performance is the actual achievement of employees compared to the expected achievements of employees. Expected work performance is a standard achievement compiled as a reference so that it can see employee performance by its position compared to the standards made. In addition, the performance of these employees can also be seen against that of other employees. According to Mangkunegara (2017), performance results from work quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties according to his responsibilities.

Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment has an important role because it can encourage a sense of attachment and loyalty from an employee to his company and as a driver to perform optimally.

According to Allen & Meyer (1990), organizational commitment is the attitude that employees have to remain loyal to the company and be willing to keep working as well as possible. Commitment is divided into three dimensions: affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuation commitment. Affective commitment is a person's emotional attachment to their organization through feelings of love for the organization. Normative commitment is a moral dimension based on a sense of obligation and responsibility to the organization that employs it, and continued commitment is a person's perception of the costs and risks of leaving the current organization. (Allen & Meyer, 1993) in (Aiyub et al, 2021). At the same time, Luthans (2011) defines organizational commitment as a strong desire to remain a member of a particular organization, striving according to organizational desires certain beliefs, and acceptance of organizational values and goals.

Employee Engagement

Employee engagement or employee engagement is an aspect that the company must consider. Because if an employee has a strong sense of engagement towards work and the company, it will increase commitment, loyalty, and even performance to the company. (Kahn, 1990 in Setyowati, 2018) Defines employee engagement as "being fully physically, cognitively and emotionally connected with their work roles." or employees who are fully connected physically, cognitively, or emotionally with their work roles. According to Schaufeli & Bakker (2004), engagement is "a positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind that is characterized by vigor, dedication and absorption.", which means a positive and happy state of mind about work, characterized by passion, dedication, and absorption. Based on the description above, it can be concluded that employee engagement is a positive and happy state of mind about work characterized by enthusiasm, dedication and absorption.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a need that must be met in every employee. With these needs met, employees will feel encouraged to like their jobs more (Hermawan, 2023). According to (Rivai, 2015), job satisfaction is a cognitive, affective, and evaluative reaction or attitude and statement that describes a pleasant or positive emotional state resulting from a person's job or work experience assessment. According to Robbins and Judge (2015), job satisfaction is a positive feeling about a person's job which results from evaluating his characteristics. According to Luthans (2011), job satisfaction is the result of employees' perception of how well their work delivers things that are considered important. Based on the description above, it can be concluded that job satisfaction is an attitude and statement that describes a pleasant or positive emotional state resulting from a person's job or work experience assessment. Herzberg (1959) in Alkaresi (2021) states that there is a two-factor theory. This theory states that satisfaction and dissatisfaction are driven by motivational factors (motivation) and hygiene factors (hygiene). Herzberg's (1959) Two-Factor Theory explains satisfaction and motivation in the workplace. Satisfaction and dissatisfaction are driven by different factors, namely motivational and hygiene factors. Motivational factors are aspects of work that make people want to perform and give satisfaction, for example, job performance, recognition, the job itself, progress, and growth within the company. At the same time, hygiene factors include aspects of the work

environment such as company policies, relationships with colleagues, working conditions, salaries, and job security.

Hypothesis Development

Based on the description of these variables, the framework of thinking in this study can be shown in Figure 1. The formulation of the hypothesis proposed in this study is as follows:

- H1: There is a significant influence of employee engagement on employee performance.
- H2: Job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance.
- H3: There is a significant influence of employee engagement on organizational commitment.
- H4: Job satisfaction has a significant effect on organizational commitment.
- H5: There is a significant influence of organizational commitment to performance employees.
- H6: There is a direct effect of employee engagement on employee performance greater than the indirect influence of employee engagement on employee performance through organizational commitment.
- H7: There is a direct effect of job satisfaction on employee performance greater than the indirect effect of job satisfaction on employee performance through organizational commitment.

Figure 1: Research model

Source: Path Analysis Model (Ghozali, 2021)

RESEARCH METHODS

This study used quantitative research methods. Quantitative methods are called scientific methods because they have fulfilled scientific principles, namely concrete/empirical, objective, measurable, rational and systematic. It is referred to as a quantitative method because research data is in the form of numbers, and analysis is done using statistics (Sugiyono, 2021). This research is located in the Office of Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia, spread across SSF work areas in 5 (five) districts spread across Indonesia. The first location is in Lima Puluh Kota Regency in West Sumatra Province; the second location is in South Lampung Regency in Lampung Province, Bima City, Bima Regency and Dompu Regency in West Nusa Tenggara Province and West Halmahera Regency in North Maluku Province. Meanwhile, the research was carried out for three months, from the beginning of August to the end of October 2023.

This study's population is employees working in the Strengthening of Social Forestry office in Indonesia. The reason for choosing employees who work in Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia is because researchers are also employees in the office, so this data and research will be easier to obtain and use as research samples. The number of employees in five districts spread across the Office of Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia is 88 employees. Ghozali (2021) stated that the sampling technique is: "To determine the sample to be used in research, there are various sampling techniques used including Probability Sampling and Non-Probability Sampling." In this study, the author used a saturated sampling technique in non-probability sampling. Sugiyono (2021) defines saturated sampling as "A sampling technique when all population members are used as samples. This is often done when the population size is relatively small or the study wants to make generalizations with very little error. Another term for saturated sampling is a census, where all population members are sampled." From the explanation of the sampling technique above, the author determines the sample with a saturated sampling method because all population members will be studied. The samples taken by the researchers were all employees working at the Office of Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia in all work locations in 5 (five) districts. Hence, the sample was as large as the population.

Table 1: Number of Employees/Population of Each District

No	District	Province	Number of Employees
1	Kabupaten Lima Puluh Kota	Sumatera Barat	14
2	Kabupaten lampung Selatan	Lampung	18
3	Kabupaten Dompu	Nusa Tenggara Barat	17
4	Kabupaten Bima	Nusa Tenggara Barat	19
5	Kabupaten Halmahera Barat	Maluku Utara	20
Total			88

Source: primary data processed, 2023

Data collection in this study was carried out by survey method through interviews and questionnaires. The interview was conducted by communicating with the Head of Regional Secretary I of BPSKL Maluku Papua using an unstructured or free model. At the same time, the questionnaire method is to be sent to respondents in each district. Before being sent to

respondents, the questionnaire is ensured to be easily understood by respondents by being arranged neatly and clearly (Sanusi, 2019). After that, the questionnaire was sent online through a website link created and distributed to all employees at the Office of Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia as respondents. The answers were provided for each question using a Likert scale of 1-5 (Sekaran, 2020). Likert scale is a scale designed to test how strongly respondents agree with statements that have been made.

RESULTS OF RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

Research Sample Description

The data collection will be from August 10, 2023, to October 10, 2023. In table 4.1, it is explained that 88 questionnaires were sent. The questionnaires returned were 79 questionnaires. So, the final sample number was 79 observations, consisting of many returned questionnaires. The questionnaire that was not filled and did not return was caused by some respondents being constrained by signal and internet networks.

Test Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Convergent Validity Test

A convergent validity test determines which gauge/indicator correlates with alternative gauges/indicators (reflective constructs) for the same construct. The convergent validity test is assessed based on the outer loading and AVE values. According to Chin (1998) and Ramli (2023), the general rules used in testing convergent validity are for confirmatory research, the loading factor value is greater than 0.7 and for early-stage research of explanatory development, the outer loading value measurement scale between 0.6 – 0.7 is still acceptable and considered sufficient and the AVE value is greater than 0.5; indicates that on average a construct describes more than half of the variants of its indicators. The following outer loading output and AVE values are passed through the PLS Algorithm procedure in the SmartPLS application.

Based on Table 2 above, it is known that the AVE root value in each indicator against the construct is greater than the AVE root value in other variables, so it can be declared that all items are valid. The construct has good discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2014).

Reliability Test

Reliability tests are performed to measure the reliability of each indicator on a variable in a construct. The construct reliability test consists of Composite and Cronbach's Alpha tests (Sugiyono, 2021). According to Ghazali & Latan (2015), the construct is declared reliable if the value of Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha is greater than 0.7 by the rule of thumbs. From the test results through the PLS Algorithm procedure in the SmartPLS application, the construct as a whole has a Composite Reliability value, and Cronbach's Alpha is greater than the rule of thumbs, which is 0.7, so it can be concluded that the construct has good reliability, as follows:

Table 3: Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha result

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Employee Engagement (X1)	0.913	0.926
Job Satisfaction (X2)	0.906	0.923
Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.952	0.959
Employee Performance (Y)	0.956	0.962

Sumber: Output SmartPLS 3.29, 2023

According to Ghazali & Latan (2015), the construct is declared reliable if the value of Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha is greater than 0.7 by the rule of thumbs. From the test results through the PLS Algorithm procedure in the SmartPLS application, the construct as a whole has a Composite Reliability value, and Cronbach's Alpha is greater than the rule of thumbs, which is 0.7, so it can be concluded that the construct has good reliability.

Test Structural Model (Inner Model)

R-Square Analysis

R-Square (R²) analysis is an analysis to determine the percentage of endogenous latent variables influenced by exogenous latent variables (Sholihin & Ratmono, 2021). The value of R-Square in this study is as follows.

Table 4: R-Square and Adjusted R-Square values

Variable	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.763	0.757
Employee Performance (Y)	0.923	0.920

Source: Output SmartPLS 3.29, 2023

Based on the R-Square value in the table above, it is known that the organizational commitment variable (Z) is 0.763, which means that 76.3% of organizational commitment variables are influenced by employee engagement and job satisfaction variables. In contrast, the rest are influenced by other variables not studied in this study. The R-Square value for the job

satisfaction variable (Y) is 0.923, which means that employee engagement variables, job satisfaction and organizational commitment influence 92.3% of employee performance variables. In contrast, the rest are influenced by other variables not studied in this study. According to Gozhali (2021), the model with the R² value criterion for the endogenous latent variable of 0.75 then the model is substantial (strong), the model with the R² value criterion for the endogenous latent variable of 0.50 then the model is moderate (moderate), and the model with the R² value criterion for the endogenous latent variable 0.25 then the model is weak. Therefore, it can be concluded that the model in this study is a moderate (medium) model.

Predictive Relevance Analysis (Q2)

Predictive Relevance (Q2) is a test conducted to see the model's prediction capability generated through the Blindfolding procedure in the SmartPLS application by looking at the Q-Square value (Ghozali, 2021). Hair et al. (2011) explain that a model with a Q-Square value greater than 0 indicates that the model has predictive relevance; conversely, a model with a Q-Square value less than 0 indicates that the model does not have predictive relevance. The value of Q-Square (Q2) through the blindfolding procedure can be seen as follows.

Figure 3: Result of Blindfolding

Table 5: Q-Square value (Q2) via Blindfolding

Variable	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1 SSE/SSO)
Employee Engagement (X1)	948.000	948.000	
Job Satisfaction (X2)	1.027.000	1.027.000	
Organizational Commitment (Z)	790.000	375.428	0.525
Employee Performance (Y)	1.185.000	505.826	0.573

Source: Output SmartPLS 3.29, 2023

Based on the table above, it is known that the value of Q-Square (Q2) in the endogenous latent variable, namely employee performance of 0.573, is greater than 0. So, it can be concluded that the model in this study has good predictive relevance. The value of R-Square (Q2) can also be determined using the Stone-Geisser Q Square Test formula as follows:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R_1^2) (1 - R_2^2)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0,923) (1 - 0,763)$$

$$Q^2 = 0,982.$$

Based on the calculation above, it is known that the Q-Square (Q2) value of 0.982 is more than 0, so it can be concluded that the model in this study can explain research data and has relevant predictive value.

Hypothesis testing

The hypothesis test in this study was conducted to assess the significance of the influence between exogenous latent variables on endogenous latent variables by looking at the value of Path Coefficients through the Bootstrapping procedure in the SmartPLS application. The approach used in assessing the hypothesis test is by looking at the Original Sample value showing the direction of research, whether positive or negative, and the T-statistic and P-value showing the significance level of the influence between latent variables.

Figure 4: Result of Bootstrapping

Table 6: Value of Path Coefficient via Bootstrapping

Variable	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
Employee Engagement → Employee Performance	0.275	0.280	0.054	5.103	0.000
Employee Engagement → Organizational Commitment	0.225	0.226	0.068	3.313	0.001
Job Satisfaction → Employee Performance	0.302	0.307	0.071	4.247	0.000
Job Satisfaction → Organizational Commitment	0.693	0.695	0.067	10.357	0.000
Organizational Commitment → Employee Performance	0.458	0.447	0.063	7.211	0.000

Table 7: Value of Specific Indirect Effect via Bootstrapping

Variable	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
EE → KO → Y	0.103	0.101	0.033	3.150	0.002
KK → KO → Y	0.317	0.310	0.051	6.214	0.000

Source: Output SmartPLS 3.29, 2023

DISCUSSION

Employee Engagement on Employee Performance

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it is known that employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. In other words, hypothesis one is accepted. This result can be interpreted that employee engagement is an employee's attachment to work, where strong engagement at work can encourage employees to work better to improve the resulting performance; according to Schaufeli & Bakker (2004), when an employee has a positive and happy state of mind about his work that can foster enthusiasm, dedication and absorption in work so that this is expected to improve performance. The results of this study are not in line with research conducted by Sari (2021), which states that employee engagement has no significant influence on Employee Performance. The data collected did not prove the relationship between employee engagement and performance. Sulistiono et al. (2019) added that the three dimensions of employee engagement, vigor, dedication, and absorption, significantly influence Employee Performance. Based on the relationship between these two variables, a hypothesis is proposed: Employee engagement has a significant influence on employee performance.

The results of research conducted by Alkaresi (2021) found that employee engagement significantly impacts Employee Performance. So, from the results of this study, it is explained that engagement significantly influences employee performance in completing every job assigned to him. H1 acceptance is also supported by field data, such as questionnaires that respondents have filled out. Statistics on the frequency of responses to statements for the employee engagement construct consisting of 12 questions representing the dimensions of passion, dedication and absorption on a Likert scale of 1-5.

Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

Based on the hypothesis test conducted, the results show a positive and significant influence between Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance; this shows that hypothesis two is accepted. The acceptance of the second hypothesis (H2), which states that Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on performance, indicates that company facilities and policies can maximize Employee Performance, superiors routinely control the results of work that has been done and provide evaluation and fair treatment to employees can be a work motivation for employees to improve their performance. This means that if Job Satisfaction increases, Employee Performance also increases.

The theory states that the relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance has been firmly established in previous literature and research. Employees whose needs are met by the company will feel satisfaction and can improve their performance in line with the research of Adhan et al. (2020), which states that there is a positive and significant relationship between job satisfaction and performance.

The results of this study are also in line with Putra et al. (2020) and Tho'in & Muliastari (2020), who found a positive and significant relationship between job satisfaction and performance. This was also revealed by Hartawan & Sriathi (2023) through their latest research, who found a positive and significant relationship between part of Herzberg's (1959) two-factor theory and Employee Performance. This theory explains satisfaction and motivation at work. Satisfaction and dissatisfaction are driven by different factors, namely motivational and hygiene factors. Motivational factors are aspects of work that make people want to perform and give satisfaction, for example, job performance, recognition, the job itself, progress, and growth within the company. At the same time, hygiene factors include aspects of the work environment such as company policies, relationships with colleagues, working conditions, salaries, and job security. The results of this study are not in line with the research conducted by Sulistiono et al. (2019), which found no positive or significant influence between Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance. Job Satisfaction indicates that the higher the Satisfaction employees feel, the better their performance will be. The acceptance of the second hypothesis (H2) is also supported by field data, in this case, questionnaires that the respondents have filled out.

Organizational Commitment to Employee Performance

Based on testing the third hypothesis, empirical evidence was obtained that Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. Thus, hypothesis three is accepted. The results of this study indicate that the higher the Organizational Commitment of employees, the better their performance will be. This is evidenced by Noviardy and Aliya's (2020) research, which found a positive and significant relationship between organizational commitment and employee performance. Theoretically, organizational commitment has a relationship with performance. Tho'in and Muliastari (2020) revealed that commitment significantly affects performance and that the higher the value of organizational commitment, the more Employee Performance increases. In line with the research conducted by Putra et al. (2020), it also revealed a positive and significant influence between organizational commitment and employee performance. Research by Adhan et al. (2020) also states that an individual with high Organizational Commitment will show positive behavior toward the organization, give the best ability he can, sacrifice, have a high level of loyalty to the organization, and be willing to remain in the organization. The results of the study also support the research findings on the third hypothesis, namely Setyowati (2018), Destika (2022) and Dami et al. (2022), which also concluded that Organizational Commitment has an effect on performance but does not line with research conducted by Chaerunissa & Pancasasti (2021) which found that there is no influence of organizational commitment on performance. Organizational commitment owned by an employee is shown by employees who feel emotionally attached to the organization; then, employees feel the organization is important to

themselves. When employees feel the organization has an important meaning, they will tend to be earnest in completing their tasks so that employees can achieve the targets set by the organization. The acceptance of the third hypothesis (H3) is also supported by field data, in this case, the questionnaires that respondents have filled out with indicators regarding affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuation commitment.

Employee Engagement in Organizational Commitment

Allen & Meyer (1990) stated that Organizational Commitment could be a psychological behavior that explains employee behavior towards the organization. In contrast, employee *engagement* is a positive psychological behavior that inspires employees to give their opinions enthusiastically and prepare themselves emotionally, cognitively, and physically to do their jobs (Priambodo, 2021). Research conducted on employees at the Strengthening of Social Forestry office in Indonesia shows that organizational commitment is one of the important factors. When employees feel attached to the organization by showing dedication, devoting great energy to carrying out a job, and a desire to give more time to complete work to achieve goals, the employee shows great commitment to the organization where he works. According to the analysis results in this study, the original sample value of the employee engagement variable on Organizational Commitment was 0.225 with a positive direction, the T-statistic value was $3.313 > 1.96$, and the P-value value was $0.001 < 0.05$. Therefore, it can be concluded that hypothesis four is accepted, which means employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment at the Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia office. In addition, the research findings on hypothesis four found that previous studies have found that employee engagement has a significant effect on Organizational Commitment. The results of this study are supported by Destika's research (2022), which states that employees with a high level of engagement can make an effort to work harder and can work with the results needed, even exceeding expectations; on the contrary, employees with low engagement levels, have low enthusiasm and commitment to the organization. Meanwhile, employee Organizational Commitment at the Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia office is based on employees' commitment to the organization, so they have strong trust and want to give more effort.

In line with Setyowati's research (2018), which states that two of the three characteristics of engagement, namely vigor and dedication, have a strong and positive significant relationship with organizational commitment, Research that has been conducted on employees of the Strengthening of Social Forestry office in Indonesia also uses the same three aspects, namely vigor, dedication, and absorption. However, the difference is that these three aspects affect organizational commitment because they underlie the variable indicators of employee engagement and have proven to have significant results affecting organizational commitment. Employees with a high level of attachment can have a strong commitment to be responsible for their work, giving more effort to achieve results that exceed expectations and commitment to stay in the organization for a long time. The acceptance of the fourth hypothesis (H4) is also supported by field data, in this case, questionnaires that respondents have filled out.

Job Satisfaction on Organizational Commitment

Based on the results of the fifth hypothesis test, it shows the original sample value of 0.693 with a positive direction, a T-Statistic value of $10.357 > 1.96$, and a P-Values value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it is concluded that hypothesis five is accepted. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment in the office and strengthening social forestry in Indonesia. This shows that the company has behaved fairly and is trying to meet employee expectations by compensating for employees' behavior and responsibility. However, over time, there are still some employees who feel dissatisfied. Judging from the respondents' answers, it can affect each employee's commitment level.

Adhan et al. (2020) found that job satisfaction positively affects organizational commitment. Job satisfaction is the most important influence on an organization's affective commitment. The higher the Job Satisfaction employees feel, the better their commitment to the organization. The results of this study are also in line with Hartawan & Riathi's (2023) research, which states that Job Satisfaction has a positive effect on organizational commitment. These results indicate that the Job Satisfaction felt by employees influences organizational commitment. This shows that the company should optimize employee job satisfaction to maximize organizational commitment. Unlike the research findings that support the fifth hypothesis, Priambodo's (2021) research results are not in line with this study, which finds that job satisfaction does not affect organizational commitment. This happens because the impact of employee expectations on what he expects from his job can change over time.

Organizational Commitment mediates employee engagement on Employee Performance.

The results of the sixth hypothesis test showed an Original Sample value of 0.103 with a positive direction, a T-statistic value of $3.150 > 1.96$, and a P-value of $0.002 < 0.05$. So, it can be concluded that hypothesis six is accepted. Employee engagement positively and significantly affects Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment as mediation at the Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia office. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, Organizational Commitment successfully mediates the effect of employee engagement on Employee Performance. On the direct effect, research findings found that employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. Furthermore, research findings found the same results on the indirect effect: employee engagement also had a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment. According to Subagyo (2018), full mediation means that the independent variable cannot affect the dependent variable significantly without going through the mediator variable. Therefore, the test results prove that the role of Organizational Commitment has succeeded in fully mediating the influence of employee engagement on Employee Performance.

The results of this study also show that the role of Organizational Commitment is very significant in mediating the relationship between employee engagement and Employee Performance. Employee engagement is an employee's attachment to work, where strong engagement at work can encourage employees to work better to increase commitment and

resulting performance; according to Schaufeli & Baker (2004), an employee who has a positive and happy state and mind at work can foster enthusiasm, dedication and absorption in work so that this is expected to improve performance. This aligns with Sari's research (2021), which states that the indirect influence between employee *engagement* variables on employee performance mediated by organizational commitment is positive and significant. This study also supports research conducted by Aiyub et al. (2021), which reveals that organizational commitment can mediate between employee engagement relationships and Employee Performance.

Organizational Commitment mediates Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance.

Based on the testing results, the seventh hypothesis shows the Original Sample value of 0.317 with a positive direction, a T-statistic value of $6.214 > 1.96$, and a P-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Therefore, it can be concluded that hypothesis seven is accepted. Job Satisfaction positively and significantly affects Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment as mediation at the Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia office. The results of this study show that the level of Job Satisfaction of employees in the company can determine the level of Employee Performance. The higher the employee Job Satisfaction, the more it increases Employee Performance to increase organizational commitment. Based on the results of the hypothesis testing conducted, Organizational Commitment successfully mediates the effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance. According to Ngatno (2015), the mediation variable is a variable that is located between independent variables and dependent variables so that the independent variable does not directly explain or affect the dependent variable. In direct effect, research findings found that Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance.

Furthermore, the indirect effect of research findings found the same results, where Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment. Thus, the results of this study show that the role of organizational commitment partially mediated the effect of job satisfaction on employee performance. The results of this study are also in line with research conducted by Hartawan Sriathi (2023), which found that organizational commitment can significantly mediate the effect of job satisfaction on employee performance. The results of his research show that to obtain good employee performance, the company needs to increase employee satisfaction so that employees can have organizational commitment. Research by Son et al. (2020) also revealed a significant influence on organizational commitment variables mediating Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study show that employee engagement and Job Satisfaction can increase Employee Performance; Organizational Commitment can also indirectly mediate between employee engagement and Employee Performance and mediate between job satisfaction and Employee Performance. Based on the results of data analysis from the observation of a sample of 79 respondents through questionnaires that have been distributed to employees of the Office of Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia spread across SSF work areas in 5 (five)

districts spread across Indonesia, it can be concluded that:

1. Employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. This means that employee engagement is an employee's attachment to work, where strong engagement can encourage employees to work better to improve the resulting performance.
2. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. This shows that if employee Job Satisfaction increases, then Employee Performance gets better, too.
3. Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. This shows that the higher the Organizational Commitment of employees, the better their performance will be.
4. Employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment. This shows that when employees feel attached to the organization by showing dedication, they show great commitment to the organization where they work.
5. Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment. This shows that the higher the Job Satisfaction employees feel, the better their commitment to the organization.
6. Organizational Commitment successfully mediates Employee engagement on Employee Performance. This shows that strong engagement can encourage employees to work better, increasing commitment and resulting performance.
7. Organizational Commitment successfully mediates Job Satisfaction to Employee Performance. This shows that the level of Job Satisfaction of employees in the company can determine the level of Employee Performance. The higher the employee Job Satisfaction, the more it increases Employee Performance to increase organizational commitment.

Research Limitations

This study contains several limitations, including:

1. The selection of research samples was only carried out at the Office of Strengthening of Social Forestry in Indonesia, so the results of this study could not generalize Employee Performance as a whole. In other words, this research was still within a limited scope.
2. Data collection takes a long time because of questionnaires sent to respondents in their respective work areas through website links. When distributing questionnaires, researchers only control through Google Drive, so researchers cannot be sure whether all respondents fill out the questionnaire as experienced.

Suggestion

Suggestions based on some limitations are as follows:

1. The recommendation for future research is to expand the scope of respondents, such as large companies spread throughout Indonesia that have been operating longer.
2. Future research should add dimensions that exist in each construct so that testing of constructs can be done in detail; this will clarify the research results on each construct.
3. Future research is expected to develop factors that indirectly influence Employee Performance in addition to the Organizational Commitment examined in this study.
4. Future research is expected to improve the quality of similar research by adding other variables to test for employee performance improvement.

References

- 1) Adhan, Muhammad. Prayogi, M. A. Siswadi, Y. (2020). Peran Mediasi Organizational Commitment pada Pengaruh Job Satisfaction terhadap Kinerja Dosen Tetap Universitas Swasta di Kota Medan. *Jurnal Samudra Ekonomi dan Bisnis* Vol. 11, No. 1. Universitas Muhammadiyah Sumatera Utara. Medan.
- 2) Aiyub, Yusuf, E.M., Bintan, R., Adnan., Azhar. (2021). The Effect of Employee Engagement on Employee Performance with Organizational Commitment as an Intervening Variable and Perceived Organization Support as a Moderating Variable at The Regional Secretariat of Bieuen District. *Jurnal Visioner & Strategis* Volume 10, Nomor 2. Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Malikusaleh. Aceh.
- 3) Alkaresi, R. (2021). Pengaruh Employee Engagement dan Komitmen Kerja Terhadap Employee Performance di Hotel Pangeran Pekanbaru Riau. *Skripsi Universitas Islam Riau*. Pekanbaru.
- 4) Allen & Meyer. (1990). The Measurement and Antecedents of Affective, Continuance and Normative Commitment to The Organization. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*. Volume 63. 1–18.
- 5) Allen & Meyer. (1993). Organizational Commitment: Evidence of Career Stage Effects. *Journal of Business Research*. 26. 49–61.
- 6) Badrianto, Yan. & Maryadi, Adi. (2023). Pengaruh Employee Engagement terhadap Employee Performance dengan Job Satisfaction sebagai Variabel Intervening. *Journal of Management & Business*. Volume 6 Issue 2.
- 7) Chaerunissa, E. & Pancasasti, R. (2021). Pengaruh Employee Engagement dan Komitmen Organization Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Melalui Job Satisfaction Pegawai Sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi pada Departemen Operasi PT Cogindo Daya Bersama PLTU Pelabuhan Ratu). *Jurnal Riset Bisnis dan Manajemen Tirtayasa*. Pascasarjana Magister Manajemen Universitas Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa. Banten.
- 8) Dami, W. D., FoEh, J. E., Manafe, H. A. (2022). Pengaruh Employee Engagement, Komitmen Organisasi dan Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Employee Performance Melalui Kepuasan Kerja Sebagai Variabel Mediasi (Suatu Kajian Studi Literatur Manajemen Sumberdaya Manusia). *Jurnal Pascasarjana Magister Manajemen*. Universitas Katolik Widya Mandira. Kupang.
- 9) Dessler, G. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia* (Edisi 14). Salemba Empat. Jakarta.
- 10) Destika. (2022). Pengaruh Employee Engagement Terhadap Employee Performance dengan Komitmen Organisasi Sebagai Variabel Moderasi Diera Covid-19 (Studi Kasus pada DPMPTSP Kabupaten Pesisir Barat). *Skripsi Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Islam*. Universitas Islam Negeri Raden Intan. Lampung.

- 11) Ghozali, Imam. (2021). Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program IBM SPSS 26, Edisi 10, Buku. Semarang. Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- 12) Ghozali, Imam & Latan, Imam. (2015). Konsep, Teknik, Aplikasi Menggunakan Smart PLS 3.0 Untuk Penelitian Empiris. Semarang: BP Undip.
- 13) Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2011). PLS-SEM: Indeed, a silver bullet. *Journal of Marketing theory and Practice*, 19(2), 139-152.
- 14) Hali, M. A. (2019). Pengaruh Employee Engagement Terhadap Employee Performance Melalui Komitmen Organisasi (Studi pada Divisi Produksi PT. Indo Putra Harapan Sukses Makmur). *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen Volume 7 Nomor 1*. Jurusan Manajemen Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Negeri Surabaya. Surabaya.
- 15) Hartawan, A. A. & Sriathi, A. A. (2023). Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Employee Performance dengan Organizational Commitment sebagai Mediasi di PT. Angsa Kusuma Indah Denpasar. *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Udayana*. Denpasar.
- 16) Hermawan, A. Sebastian. (2023). Pengaruh Organizational Culture dan Job Satisfaction Terhadap Employee Performance dengan Employee Engagement sebagai Variabel Mediasi di PT. Lucky Textile Semarang. Skripsi Universitas Islam Sultan Agung. Semarang.
- 17) Henseler, J., et al. (2014). Common Beliefs and Reality about Partial Least Squares: Comments on Rönkkö & Evermann (2013), *Organizational Research Methods*, 17(2): 182-209.
- 18) Herzberg, F. (1959). *The Motivation to Work* (2nd ed). NewYork: John Wiley & Sons.
- 19) Kadri, A. Firgandhini., Ibrahim, H. M., Irwanan, Andri., Prasetianingrum, Septyana. (2023). Peran Job Satisfaction dalam Memediasi Pengaruh antara Employee Engagement terhadap Kinerja Pegawai di Lingkungan Pemerintah Distrik Jayapura Utara. *Journal of Economics Review Volume. 3 No. 1*.
- 20) Luthans, F. (2011). *Organizational Behavior: an Evidence-Based Approach*. McGraw Hill/Irwin. New York.
- 21) Mahmudi. (2019). *Manajemen Kinerja Sektor Publik*. UPP STIM YKPN. Yogyakarta.
- 22) Mangkunegara, Anwar. P. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan* (Edisi 14). Remaja Rosdakarya: Bandung.
- 23) Mathis, L. R. & Jackson, H. J. (2016). *Human Resource Management* (edisi 14). Salemba Empat. Jakarta.
- 24) Ngatno. (2015). *Analisis Data Variabel Mediasi dan Moderasi dalam Riset Bisnis dengan Program SPSS*. CV. Farisma Indonesia, Yogyakarta.
- 25) Noviardy, Andrian. & Aliya, Sabeli. (2020). Pengaruh Employee Engagement dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Employee Performance di Bidang Perkebunan Kelapa Sawit (Studi Empiris pada PT. Suryabumi Agrolanggeng di Sumatera Selatan). *Journal Management, Business and Accounting Vol. 19, No. 3*. Universitas Bina Darma. Palembang.
- 26) Noercahyo, U. S., Maarif, M. S., Sumertajaya, I. M. (2021). The Role of Employee Engagement on Job Satisfaction and Its Effect on Organizational Performance. *Journal of Applied Management*, Vol. 19, No. 2. Institut Pertanian Bogor. Bogor.
- 27) Priambodo, P. A.T, 2021. Pengaruh Employee Engagement Terhadap Organizational Commitment dan Employee Performance: Job Satisfaction Sebagai Variabel Mediasi (Studi pada Karyawan Perusahaan QHomeMart Yogyakarta). *Jurnal Fakultas Bisnis dan Ekonomika*. Universitas Islam Indonesia. Yogyakarta.
- 28) Putra, Anjas. K. Jaya, I. Wilian. R. (2020). Pengaruh Job Satisfaction Terhadap Kinerja dengan Komitmen Organisasi Sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi pada Mitra Bangunan Kota Jambi). *Jurnal Dinamika Manajemen Universitas Jambi*. Vol. No. 1, Januari – April 2020. Jambi.

- 29) Ramli, Azhari. Afrizal. (2023). Pengaruh Quality of Work Life dan Job Satisfaction terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior PNS Millennial dimediasi oleh Happiness at Work pada Sekretariat Daerah Provinsi Maluku Utara. Tesis Universitas Khairun. Ternate.
- 30) Rivai, V. (2015). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia untuk Perusahaan: dari Teori ke Praktik. Rajawali Pers. Jakarta.
- 31) Rizky, Yunita. Maudy. (2020). Pengaruh Employee Engagement dan Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Employee Performance CV. Amifa Keluarga Lestari Pekanbaru. Skripsi Fakultas Ekonomi dan Ilmu Sosial. Universitas Negeri Sultan Syarif Kasim Riau. Pekanbaru.
- 32) Rizwandha, M. F. Izza. (2020). Pengaruh Employee Engagement dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Employee Performance (Studi pada KSPPS BMT Peta Tulungagung). Skripsi Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim. Malang.
- 33) Robbins, P. Stephen. & Judge, A. Timothy. 2015. Perilaku Organisasi (terjemahan) Edisi 16. Penerbit Salemba Empat: Jakarta.
- 34) Sanusi, A. (2019). Metodologi Penelitian Bisnis; Disertai Contoh Proposal Penelitian Bidang Ilmu Ekonomi dan Manajemen. Malang. Salemba Empat.
- 35) Sari, Mayriza. (2021). Pengaruh Employee Engagement Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Melalui Komitmen Organisasi Sebagai Variabel Intervening di Bagian Rawat Jalan RSUD H. Abdul Manap Kota Jambi. Jurnal Manajemen Terapan dan Keuangan, Vol. 10, No. 03. Jambi.
- 36) Schaufeli, W. B. & Bakker, A. B. (2004). UWES - Utrecht Work Engagement Scale: Test Manual. *Unpublished Manuscript*: Department of Psychology, Utrecht University.
- 37) Sekaran, U. (2020). Research Method for Business, Edisi 8, Buku. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- 38) Setyowati, S. (2018). Pengaruh Employee Engagement Terhadap Employee Performance Dengan Komitmen Organisasi Sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi pada Karyawan PT. Tiga Manunggal Textil Salatiga). Skripsi Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis. Universitas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta. Yogyakarta.
- 39) Sholihin, Mahfud. & Ratmono, Dwi. (2021). Analisis SEM-PLS dengan Warp-PLS 7.0 untuk Hubungan Nonlinier dalam Penelitian Sosial dan Bisnis (Edisi 2). Andi Offset. Yogyakarta.
- 40) Subagyo, Masruroh, N. A., dan Bastian, I. (2018). Akuntansi Manajemen Berbasis Desain. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press.
- 41) Sugiyono. (2021). Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif Kualitatif dan R & D. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 42) Sulistiono, D., Hermawan, A., Sukmawati, A. (2019). The Effect of Empowerment and Employee Engagement on Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment and Its Impact on Performance of PTPN V. Jurnal Manajemen dan Agriisnis, Vol. 16 No. 3. Institut Pertanian Bogor.
- 43) Tho'in, M. & Muliarsi, D. (2020). Analysis of Work Satisfaction, Organizational Commitments and Work Engagement Effect Toward Employee Performance in Sharia Banks. International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research. Institut Teknologi Bisnis AAS Indonesia. Surakarta.